

Equitable and Inclusive Education in NEP 2020: Provisions, Challenges and Implementation

Nibedita Priyadarshani

Assistant Professor (Education)

Rani Dharma Kunwar Govt. Degree College

Khanpur, Dallawala, Dist- Haridwar-247663

Email-nibeditapriyadarshani@gmail.com

Received: 25/01/2024

1st BPR: 09/02/2024

2nd BPR: 16/02/2024

Accepted: 28/02/2024

Abstract

Main purpose of the present research paper is to know the Provision of equitable and inclusive education in NEP 2020. Aim of this paper is to discuss the challenges of implementing equitable and inclusive education. The possible strategies can be adopted for implementing equitable and inclusive education in our country. Low enrolment of scheduled caste, scheduled tribe, other backward class, women, minorities and person with disabilities are the challenges before educational institutions. Inappropriate implementation strategy, lack of awareness in school authorities and teachers about the needs of PWD, improper implementation strategies of government strategies and economic disparities are obstacles in India on the path of equitable and inclusive education. Some areas are declared as special education zone for providing extra facilities to the weaker sections. Cross disability training and home based education and development of high quality modules on sign language are some of the provision in national education policy.

Keywords: Inclusive Education, Equitable, Special Education Zone And Cross Disability Training.

Introduction

Education plays a decisive role in nation building. This is the pious duty of the policy makers to frame policies to ensure that all children receive quality education as per their ability and interest without any discrimination of caste, creed, class, religion or gender i.e the policy makers should ensure the universalization of education that would in turn bring equality and equity in society by strengthening and empowering the citizen to enable them to contribute in nation building.

Since independence the govt. is making continuous effort to bring educational equality for all its citizens but till date disparity exists in educational level indicators in different States and union territories. Some States are doing better than others while on the other hand in some States the level is much below than the national average. This educational disparity is not only among States but even within the state. It exists in great measure among different districts, regions, which is a matter of concern for all.

Status of equitable and inclusive education after independence

In September 2015, all countries including India adopted 17 sustainable development goals (SDGs) of the 2030 Agenda for sustainable development at an historic UN summit. Out of these 17 goals, the fourth one is 'quality education for all'. The global education development agenda seeks to ensure by 2030 inclusive and equitable education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all. Keeping in mind the Indian constitution advocates equal educational opportunities to all its citizens without any barrier of caste, class or gender. Committees like University Education Commission (1948), Secondary Education Commission (1952), Kothari Commission (1964-66), and National policy

education (1968), Review of National Policy Education (1986), Acharya Rammurti committee, 1990, Programme of Action (1992) have been formed after independence to bring reform in education system. Among these committees Kothari Commission (1964-66) suggested equalization of educational opportunities by minimizing interstate differences by development of the weaker section of the community should be undertaken by central government. In 1986, National policy in Education suggested to establish rural universities and open universities with the purpose to provide education to masses. Another recommendation was to provide equal opportunities to the disparities. Implementation of all those recommendations could not bring successful result. In 2020, National education policy has made a focus on all the aspects of education right from primary education to higher education and professional education. Proper implementation of NEP, 2020 is going to be a revolutionary step to modernize India. No doubt this initiative will make India Vishwa Guru in future.

NEP 2020 and Goals of Equitable and inclusive education

Regarding equitable and inclusive education NEP2020 states that "The education aim to benefit India's children so that no child loses any opportunity to learn and excel because of circumstances of birth or background." The main focus of NEP2020 is to provide equal educational opportunities to the deprived section society. In order to achieve this goal, following measures are formulated -

1. To explore deprived section students' potential and creativity with provisions to provide equal educational opportunities.
2. To provide quality education to economically disadvantaged group of population, particularly women, transgender, SC, ST, OBC, minorities, people belonging to villages, small town and remote areas, disabled people, migrant communities, low income households and children in vulnerable situation, orphans, deprived children, child beggar and children of trafficking victims.

Challenges of equitable and inclusive education

Following challenges are before India for bringing an equitable and inclusive education

1. **Low enrolment of SC, ST and PWD** – UDISE 2016-17 data states that enrolment of SC children at primary level is about 19.6 % but their share decreases to 17.3% at the higher secondary level. Similar low enrolment is found among schedule tribe student is from 10.6 percent to 6.8 percent and also in case of children with disability from 1.1 percent to 0.25 percent declines. NIEPA, 2020 reported in all the three categories women are more affected. In comparison to boy, girls have fewer enrollments.
2. **Inclusion of children with special needs** - According to National sample survey, 2018 48.8 percent of persons with disabilities are literate. Only 62.9 % of those aged between 3 to 35 years have been enrolled in a regular school. Goyal (2020) highlighted low retention rate of CWDs of 23.1 percent of enrolled children are attending school.
3. **Lack of awareness in school authorities and teachers about the needs of PWD**
4. **Inappropriate environment in schools for children with disabilities**- Goyal (2020) found in his study inaccessibility in the school campus for children with disabilities is the major obstacle in the path of equity and inclusive education
5. **Lack of proper implementation strategy of government schemes**- In order to increase the enrolment of disadvantaged group government is implementing various schemes. But due to lack of proper implementation strategy, people do not avail these facilities. So there is no change found in their educational status.
6. **Economic disparities**- India has hi-tech metro-city on the contrary there are villages, small towns where even roads, electricity and clean drinking water is not available. Economic Times 2020 stated that in India rich population of 1% who holds 40% of the total wealth of the country. There are large number of beggars, migrant labourers and children trafficking who are not able to afford

two meals a day. These economic disparities are also hindrance on the path of educational equality and inclusive education.

Implementation strategies

Since the implementation tactics of any policy determine its effectiveness, the policy provisions in NEP 2020 should be thoroughly considered and examined. The main obstacle to putting this concept into practice is the paucity of funding for building infrastructure and facilities in schools, colleges and institutions. The following tactics for inclusive and equitable education will be put into practice.

- The scholarship amount for low-income Schedule Caste children should be increased, and parents should be encouraged to apply for their ward's admission to the school, in order to strengthen and boost their GER.
- Secondary and postsecondary students who live far from schools and institutions should have access to free dorms and boarding accommodations.
- The medium of instruction in tribal communities with higher than usual percentages of ST pupils should be tribal language. Teachers who are conversant in their language ought to be hired for this.
- In order to improve the socio-economic situation of children in this community, several continuing "programmatic interventions" will be conducted in order to expand educational possibilities and provide pertinent education to schedule tribal children.
- The most effective way to create a friendly environment is for teachers to model positive behaviour for their students who belong to Scheduled Caste and Scheduled Tribe communities.
- School personnel should generally work to ensure that there is no discrimination against children from SC, ST, and other communities.
- It is best to refrain from using disparaging language or caste designations when naming children or making roll calls.
- Teachers should guide every student equally to engage in school-sponsored extracurricular activities as well as games.
- It should be scheduled for staff school teachers and parents of SC and ST children to meet on a regular basis. The specifics of the programme to support education among SC and ST people should be discussed at these meetings. They ought to be reminded of the importance of continuing their children's education. It is especially important to encourage them to support females' education.
- To create a barrier-free environment for people with disabilities: Schools and institutions need to make structural modifications, which will cost money and need commitment to do this work seriously.
- NEP2020 placed a strong emphasis on the contribution that women make to society, as they account for half of all socioeconomic disadvantaged groups (SEDGs). In order to improve female students' access to education, enrollment, retention rates, and learning outcomes, the policy also states that the Government of India will establish a "Gender Inclusion Fund" to increase the country's ability to offer equitable, high-quality education to all girls and transgender students.

In order to genuinely transform their educational landscape, NEP2020 states that areas of the nation with a sizable population from the SEDGs that are educationally disadvantaged should be designated as Special Education Zones (SEZs), where all programmes and policies are implemented to the fullest extent possible through additional coordinated efforts. To provide kids with more access to high-quality education, free boarding facilities will be constructed in places that are currently underprivileged, such as aspirational districts, Kasturba Gandhi Balika and Jawahar Navodaya Vidyalayas, Kendriya Vidyalayas in the special education zone, and other disadvantageous areas. Accessibility will be improved by programmes like scholarships, financial aid to encourage parents to enroll their children in school, transportation bicycles, etc. that has dramatically expanded the participation of SEDGs in the educational system in particular places.

Provision for Person with disability

Disabled children who are around 2.2% of the population in the mainstream education, the most challenging and significant task is to enable them participate equally at all levels of educational opportunities. NEP 2020 accepted all special instruction as laid by The Rights of Persons with Disabilities Act, 2016 for providing quality education. These are as follows:-

- (i) Admit the disable children without discrimination and provide education and opportunities for sports and recreation activities equally with others
- (ii) Make buildings and campus and various facilities accessible.
- (iii) Provide reasonable accommodation according to the individual's requirements
- (iv) Provide necessary support individualized or otherwise in environments that maximize academic and social development consistent with the goal of inclusion.
- (v) Ensure that the education to persons who are blind or deaf or both is imparted in the most appropriate languages and modes and means of communication
- (vi) Detect specific learning disabilities in children at the earliest and take suitable pedagogical and other measures to overcome them
- (vii) Monitor participation, progress in terms of attainment levels and completion of education in respect of every student with disability.
- (viii) Provide transportation facilities to the children with disabilities and also the attendant of the children with disabilities having high support needs

The New Education Policy has given importance that while preparing the National Curriculum Framework, NCERT will ensure that consultations are held with expert bodies such as National Institutes of DEPWD. The real motto of it is to enable the children with disability will fully participate in the regular schooling process from foundational stage to higher education. The NEP2020 completely accepted the directions of RPWD Act, 2016 and endorses all its recommendations with regard to education of disabled children.

Cross disability training

This policy has highlighted to appoint additional special educators with cross-disability training in school education. Divyang children should be given one to one teachers and tutors and they should be provided appropriate infrastructure and technological interventions in their schools as per their requirements.

Home- based education

Home- based education is available for children with severe and profound disabilities who are unable to go to school. This education is treated as equal as regular education.

Development of high quality modules of sign language

NEP 2020 made provision to develop high quality modules of sign languages for children with communication problem. For developing the modules NOIS is entrusted for these responsibilities.

Appointment of additional special educators

Appointment of additional special educators with cross-disability training in school education is needed. Divyang children should be given one-to-one teacher and tutors. As per their requirements infrastructure facilities and technological interventions should be provided.

Provision for economically and socially disadvantaged group

Special educational zone in general, technical and vocational education institutes should be established according to the requirements of students. Open University should be promoted in these areas for access of this group.

Pragmatic interventions for upliftment of Scheduled tribe

In order to provide educational opportunities to children from tribal areas several pragmatic interventions are going on. Special mechanisms need to be developed to ensure that children belonging to tribal areas avail the benefits of these interventions. Govt. should give free facilities of hostels to tribal students. While framing curriculum, needs of tribal students should be taken seriously. If number of students is more than average in any school then their local tribal language should be medium of instruction. Teachers those have knowledge of local language should be given appointment on priority basis.

Interventions for minorities

NEP2020 also highlights underrepresentation of minorities in both school and higher education. Intervention programmes should be implemented to raise the educational status of minorities.

Programmes for OBC welfare

The 2020 National Education Policy states that extra attention would be paid to the educational possibilities of other underprivileged classes. In order to enhance the enrollment, retention, and academic performance of OBC students, the current welfare programmes for these students must to be maintained and reinforced.

Actions to address gender inequality

Almost half of all socioeconomically disadvantaged groups (SEDGs) are made up of women. The strategy also suggested that programmes and initiatives created with students from SEDGs should give special attention to girls who fall under these goals. In order to improve female students' access to, enrollment in, and output from school, the policy also stipulates that the Indian government will establish a "Gender-inclusion Fund" in order to strengthen the country's ability to offer equitable, high-quality education.

Special Education Zone (SEZ) declaration

In India, there are many different types of regional differences. To genuinely transform their educational landscape, areas of the nation with a sizable population from the SEDGs that are educationally disadvantaged should be designated as Special Education Zones (SEZs), where all programmes and policies are implemented to the fullest extent possible through additional coordinated efforts (NEP2020). Institutions of general, technical, and vocational education should be founded in accordance with student needs. In these domains, Open University ought to be encouraged.

Accommodation for students from low-income backgrounds

Students who live in places where schools are far from home should be provided with free boarding facilities, such as Jawahar Navodaya Vidyalayas. For improved enrollment and accessibility to high-quality education, aspirational districts, special education zones, and other underprivileged areas should host Kendriya Vidyalayas, Kasturba Gandhi Balika Vidyalayas, and Jawahar Navodaya Vidyalayas.

Facilities for education for socially and economically disadvantaged groups (SEDGs)

NEP2020 suggested generous scholarships and financial assistance for students who meet the SEDGs and children with physical disabilities in order to give educational facilities to pupils who are economically and socially disadvantaged. They must also be given free dormitory accommodations, technology support, guidance and counselling services.

Conclusion

Education system of a country, more or less, is a prime indicator of its development. Therefore, the most advanced countries in the world possess strong education system and it always remains their top priority. The major problem that hampers enrolment in India's education system is that the lower

strata of society, the socially and economically disadvantaged group has dwindling faith that education can lead to employment or vocation and can guarantee better future prospects for them. NEP 2020 with focus on vocational training from primary level will definitely prove game changer in the long run. The provisions given in NEP 2020 are sincere concern of the government to ensure equality and inclusion of the SEDG and PWD in the mainstream education. No doubt, it can be reiterated that the onus of success of any policy depends on its implementation, hence the input of strategy, dedication and perseverance will determine the future outcome of this policy but the detailed and meticulous provision with the aim to support and promote SEDG and PWD through equitable and inclusive education, incorporated in the NEP 2020 garner hope for better future prospects of these sections of society

References

- Baquer & Sharma (2014). Disability: Challenges Vs Responses, e book. Business Today, June 12, 2021 e- paper edition.
- Goyal, D. (2020). Assessing the level of inclusive education at the school level at India, Young voices, October 7.
- Kukreti, S. (2021). Equitable and inclusive Education in NEP 2020: Provisions, Challenges and Implementation Strategies, *National Educational policy 2020: Issues, challenges and reflections*, ISBN 978-93-91229-29-0, PP. 59-68
- National educational Policy 2020, Ministry of human Resource Development, Govt. of India, New Delhi
- NIEPA (2020). NEP2020: Implementation strategies. National Institute of Educational planning and administration, New Delhi, Oxfam Report quoted in *The Economic Times*, 20 Jan 2020 e pa per.
- Pingle, S. & Garg, I. (2015). Effect of inclusive education awareness programme on pre-service teachers, Paper presented in the European Conference on Education 2015, organized on the theme- *Education, power and Empowerment: Changing and Challenging Communities*, July 1-5, 2015
- RPWD Act (2016). *The Right of Persons with Disabilities Act 2016*, Department of Legislative, Government of India, New Delhi.
- Singh, J. D. (2016). Inclusive education in India: Concept need and challenges. *Scholarly Research Journal for Humanities, Science and English Language*, 3(13), 3222-3232.
- Sen, Malini (2007). A school for all, *Education Times, Times of India*, September 24, 2007

